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**The Business of War: A Case Study of Private Military Contractors in
Afghanistan**

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Dedication

Alhamdulillah.

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Abstract

This thesis explores the role and consequences of Private Military Contractors (PMCs) in the context of the US-led coalition in Afghanistan and the failure of their nation-building program. The analysis builds off of historical records, government reports, policy analyses, case studies, and a variety of other sources to explain just how more than \$14 trillion went sideways. The research argues that while PMCs solved the manpower shortages, the U.S. mission was frequently damaged by their use. The findings reveal that corruption, inflated costs, inadequate oversight, and a lack of accountability are systematic issues. Although the case study is concerned with Afghanistan, it recognizes the global scale of the phenomenon, with superpowers such as China and Russia increasingly relying on PMCs to serve their strategic interests both domestically and internationally. The research concludes that as long as war persists, PMCs will remain in demand. Therefore, the study calls for a new, less militarized foreign policy, which it argues should be a top priority for both the general public and decision makers.

Keywords: Private Military Contractors, Afghanistan War, U.S. Foreign Policy, War Economy.

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List of abbreviations

AVF: All Volunteer Force

DOD: Department of Defense

DOJ: Department of Justice

MNC: Multinational Corporations

NGOs: Non-governmental Organizations

FY: Fiscal Year

PMC: Private Military Contractor

PMF: Private Military Firm

SIGAR: Special Inspector General for Afghanistan Reconstruction

UN: United Nations

USA: United States of America

U.S.: United States

9/11: September 11th, 2001

1.1 General introduction

The United States war in Afghanistan, often called “America’s longest war,” officially started in 2001 after the tragic events of 9/11. In the next 20 years, U.S. foreign policy was defined by this conflict, especially in regard to the Middle East and Central Asia. It involved intense military operations, political negotiations, and the formation of an international coalition. But beyond the obvious presence of the United States military and the expected field battles, this war's outcome was shaped by another critical element that received far less public attention: the rise of private military contractors (PMCs).

Since the start of the war in Afghanistan, Pentagon spending has totaled over \$14 trillion, half of it went to defense contractors. These were private companies often hired to do military-related tasks previously handled by government employees. To understand their role, it's helpful to look at the work of Peter Warren Singer, one of the leading scholars in the field of military privatization. He defines PMCs as private companies taking on roles that have traditionally been filled by the military and intelligence agencies. His definition comes with the implication that the range of tasks performed by PMCs is vast, some of which include watching over convoys, teaching local security forces, gathering information, handling logistics, and even helping directly in battle.

In simple words, contractors are not active-duty soldiers, or government employees, but private companies and service providers, which the U.S. uses to free up troops for combat, access specialised skills, scale operations quickly, and potentially reduce costs compared to hiring permanent staff. He also pointed out a critical shift in the nature of modern wars and how they are fought. According to him, traditionally war was one in which state-controlled militaries with soldiers in uniforms fought for national interests. However, this image has completely changed in the 21st century. Today, PMCs play a primary role in warfare. In many cases, they operate

alongside or even in place of the state armies, often blurring the lines between official military personnel and private contractors.

This dissertation focuses on the use of Private Military Contractors (PMCs) during the U.S. war in Afghanistan. It explores how these private firms were used to support military operations, protect bases, train local forces, and provide supplies. While these contractors were often presented as cost-effective and necessary, the reality is much more complicated. Their presence raised many questions about accountability, transparency, and whether they truly helped or harmed the U.S. mission.

1.2 Personal Motivation

"The best minds are not in government. If any were, business would steal them away," said Ronald Reagan. I first encountered this quote at the beginning of a YouTube video, its meaning was deepened by a Vox Media documentary that explored the rise of Private Military Companies (PMCs), which led me to explore how private enterprises impact traditional government roles, especially in military operations.

As a student who's interested in geopolitics, I always wanted to understand wars. A quick web search revealed that many developed nations no longer rely only on their national armies for conflicts; instead, they have been increasingly utilizing PMC's. Then came the 2021 announcement by Biden regarding a full U.S. troop withdrawal from Afghanistan by September 11 (U.S. Department of Defense), coupled with images of Afghans attempting to flee their country on U.S. military planes at Kabul Airport, some hanging off the front wheel and others falling from the sky to their deaths after the plane took off (Al Jazeera).

These events transformed my curiosity into a focused academic project. The footage and its implications piqued my interest even further in Afghanistan, ultimately leading me to dedicate my master's dissertation to this topic.

1.3 Background to the Study

The privatization of military functions has increased dramatically in recent decades, especially after the Cold War. Governments of different parts of the world started relying more heavily on private companies to provide logistical, security, and operational support in conflict zones. The U.S. military invasion of Afghanistan in 2001 became one of the most notable examples of this trend.

From 2001 to 2021, the U.S. military presence in Afghanistan was deeply connected to private contractors. These companies were involved in nearly every aspect of the war effort, ranging from construction and logistics to intelligence and armed security. The scale of this involvement has raised critical questions about the consequences of outsourcing such war-related tasks to the private sector.

This study builds on the existing literature that has focused on the Iraq War; this research takes a different approach by narrowing the focus to the case of Afghanistan and analyzing how this model of warfare influenced U.S. strategic goals. It also tries to shed light on the less visible effects of privatization, including issues related to accountability, cost, and long-term effectiveness.

1.4 Research Questions

The aim of this dissertation is to examine the impact of private military contractors (PMCs) on the achievement of U.S. strategic objectives in Afghanistan. It investigates whether PMCs contributed to or hindered these objectives, and explores claims regarding their

cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency. Additionally, the study assesses whether their involvement led to issues such as waste, fraud, and corruption. Central to this Debate is the question of who ultimately benefited from the prolonged conflict—the Afghan people, the U.S. government, or the private firms contracted to support the war effort.

Following this, the central research question guiding this study is:

How did the use of private military contractors in Afghanistan affect U.S. strategic objectives?

To break this down further, the study also explores:

RQ1. Did PMCs support or weaken U.S. goals in Afghanistan?

RQ2. How did the lack of transparency and oversight affect their performance?

These questions aim to guide the work toward understanding not only the tactical and financial effects of PMCs but also their general impact on policy, trust, and long-term outcomes.

1.5 Research Aims

Based on the research questions, this study has the following aims:

- Shed light on an overlooked but important dimension of the war, one that has received very limited attention in public discussions and media coverage, despite its major consequences. This study aims to give the topic the academic spotlight it deserves.
- Analyze the role played by PMCs in the Afghanistan conflict and determine their impact on the U.S. mission.

- Evaluate the claims put forth by advocates for military contracting that the commercialization of government functions decreases costs and increases the quality of these services.
- Identify the hidden or indirect costs of privatization, particularly in areas like transparency and oversight.
- Contribute to broader academic discussions on the privatization of warfare by offering a focused case study on Afghanistan.

By addressing these aims, the study seeks to offer new insights into whether PMCs supported or compromised the goals of the United States in its longest and most expensive war.

1.6 Overview of the Methodology

To answer these research questions, the study relies on a review of secondary data to examine the role played by private military contractors (PMCs) in Afghanistan and their impact on the U.S. strategic objectives. The primary data source is authoritative reports from the Special Inspector General for Afghanistan Reconstruction (SIGAR), such as the 2011 and 2024 quarterly documents.

Moreover, This study collects secondary data specifically for contracts where the "place of performance" is Afghanistan, covering Fiscal Years (FY) 2002–2024, which is the duration of U.S. military involvement in the conflict. Additional evidence comes from peer-reviewed studies (e.g., Azami; Jäger and Kümmel; Schaub and Kelty), media investigations (e.g., CNBC, The Guardian), and policy analyses (e.g., Watson Institute’s Costs of War project).

In doing so, the dissertation aims to contribute to the wider debate on war privatization and whether the promise of efficiency and professionalism offered by PMCs truly matched the reality on the ground. By looking closely at the case of Afghanistan, this study hopes to shed

light on the hidden costs of outsourcing war. The costs were not just in dollars, but in trust, stability, and human lives.

1.7 Summary of the Findings

This paper has documented the enormous growth in military contracting in the post-9/11 era, as well as the reasons for that growth. It argues that the use of PMCs in Afghanistan ultimately undermined U.S. strategic objectives more than it supported them. Billions of dollars were spent on unnecessary, overpriced, or abandoned projects for it to turn out that the only beneficiaries were the contractors. While smaller actors included in the wasted war budget were held accountable, large firms were not, showing a selective and unjust accountability system within the U.S. government.

The study also reveals a deep political conflict of interest. Some members of Congress held investments in defense companies that received war contracts, and the Pentagon's "revolving door" enabled retired military officials to take positions in private firms and shape future policy. This overlap between political power and profit weakened transparency and public trust.

Many PMCs lacked the formal hiring process, and some of them were found to be engaging in unethical practices, such as employing former child soldiers or hiring poorly trained guards from disadvantaged countries to reduce the costs.

The heavy reliance on PMCs weakened the Afghan democratic state-building efforts. Instead of forming a sustainable local Afghan force, the U.S. built an army that operates with air support and intelligence whose backbone is contractors. This contributed to the Democratic Afghanistan government's rapid collapse shortly after the U.S. withdrawal and the Taliban's return to power.

Finally, contractors operated without competitive pressure, often charging inflated prices for their services. Despite promises of efficiency, PMCs were not cheaper; in fact, many contractors' personnel earned up to \$1,200 per day, far more than U.S. soldiers or even

high-ranking generals. The high salaries and flexible contracts offered by PMCs encouraged many elite soldiers to leave their national armies. For example, individuals like Erik Prince openly stated that the private sector offered far greater rewards for the same job and risk. When the best and the brightest from armies around the world are now working for PMCs, one has to wonder: Will the next military superpower be a country or a corporation?

Chapter I: The Rise of Outsourced Warfare

1.1 Introduction

This chapter explains my personal motivation for this study, provides the background to the research, and offers a general overview of the study area, making it an entry point to the dissertation. It defines what PMCs are and how they are hired through government contracts. The chapter also explores the historical roots, from early American wars to the Cold War era and beyond. Understanding this evolution makes it easier to see how military outsourcing became not only common but also crucial to U.S. operations as a result of post-Cold War downsizing and globalization.

1.2 Historical Background

To understand the shift to military privatization, it is essential to explore its historical roots. Erik Dean Prince, the American founder of Blackwater¹, famously stated in an interview with VICE Media Group that "PMCs are as American as Thanksgiving Day." Prince has controversially claimed that the English colonies, like Massachusetts Bay and Plymouth, were started by charters given by the British Crown, which he compares to modern contractors. The investors in England financed these expeditions with the expectation of returned profits, which resonates with today's PMCs goals. While Prince's example is controversial, it pointed out the profit-driven nature of both historical and modern military enterprises, demonstrating how the use of contractors in military operations can be traced back to the early days of the U.S.

As far back as the Continental Army under General Washington, contractors were hired to offer engineering expertise, drive wagons, run telegraph communications, and provide medical treatments. The Continental Congress believed that contractors should perform these duties to free up the troop units to focus on their combat roles (Zamparelli 5-6). The use of contractors can be justified since a lot of these logistical tasks were non-combat roles better suited for civilians, like driving a wagon, or were too complicated and required a specialized person in the industry like

¹ Blackwater, now known as Academi, is a PMC founded by Erik Prince in 1997. It became famous for providing security services in conflict zones like Iraq and Afghanistan.

telegraph operators. This U.S. way of fighting its wars remained mainly unchanged from the War of 1812 up until the Vietnam conflict in the 1950s. In each of the events, a significant number of contractors participated in military operations, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. U.S. Civilians Participation in Conflicts

War/Conflict	Civilians	Military	Ratio
Revolution	1,500 (est)	9,000	1:6 (est)
Mexican/American	6,000 (est)	33,000	1:6 (est)
Civil War	200,000 (est)	1 Million	1:5 (est)
World War I	85,000	2 Million	1:20
World War II	734,000	5.4 Million	1:7
Korean Conflict	156,000	393,000	1:2.5
Vietnam Conflict	70,000	359,000	1:6

Source: (Zamparelli 6)

The use of civilians in wartime was not without problems. According to Rebar, the army needed teamsters² to transport supplies during the Civil War. To encourage men to take on this difficult and sometimes dangerous job, the U.S. Army offered draft exemptions³. However, as the war continued, it became hard to find reliable teamsters, and those who were working were often difficult to manage. As a result, the military commanders replaced the civilian drivers with

² Teamsters were drivers of wagons or other vehicles, especially those transporting supplies for the military. They were crucial for moving goods and equipment during the Civil War.

³ Draft exemptions refer to legal provisions that excuse certain individuals from compulsory military service due to reasons such as medical conditions, education, and employment in critical industries.

soldiers who could not resign or disobey orders. At that time, commanders had the luxury of giving back these tasks to soldiers, who possessed the skill sets required to support contractors and carry out their tasks. Additionally, the military policy towards the employment of contractors was that the closer the function was to combat, the greater the need for soldiers rather than contractors to perform it (Rebar 3). That is to say, tasks near the front lines were considered too important to be given to contractors, who couldn't always be trusted.

However, the employment of contractors started to change over time. By the Vietnam War in 1955, the U.S. had increased its reliance on private contractors. U.S. Army Major Thomas Wilhelm noted, "There might have been a time in the past when the site of a military operation was an exclusive club for those in uniform, but those days are waning" (Zamparelli 7). In Vietnam, contractors played a direct role in supporting military operations, providing petroleum supply, maintenance, and technical support for complex military equipment (Rebar 3). Business Week Magazine even called the Vietnam conflict "war by contract" (qtd. in Zamparelli 7). Unlike the Civil War, where contractors were replaced by soldiers, in Vietnam, contractors worked side by side with the troops, they were becoming the specialists in the tools of war (Zamparelli 7).

1.3 The Cold War's Impact

Singer in his book *Corporate Warriors* argues that the international private military industry began booming by the end of the Cold War. He links the augmented growth of PMCs to the unwillingness of states to get involved in conflicts, creating a "security gap" as the old superpower balance collapsed (49). This vacuum, as Singer describes it, affected both the supply and demand of military services. In the post-Cold War era, many army forces around the world were downsized (see the graph below), providing a pool of trained professionals and surplus equipment for Private Military Firms (PMFs), significantly reducing the startup expenses, as they could hire experienced personnel and acquire equipment at lower costs.

Fig. 1. Armed forces personnel worldwide, 1990 until 2016

Source: Human Progress

Gary Jr. Schaub in his book *Controlling the Corporate Warrior* tends to agree with Singer's point that the soldiers who left or were laid off from the army formed a pool of highly skilled former military personnel (ch. 2). Unlike Singer, Schaub believes that the private military industry that exists today has its roots in the 20th century (ch. 17). In post-colonial African countries, for example, mercenaries of that time were known for mounting coups, putting down rebellions, and committing abuses (Schaub and Kelty 357).

One infamous mercenary is Mike Hoare, better known as Mad Mike. Hoare served in the British Army during the Second World War. He was then hired by Moïse Tshombe, a Congolese businessman, to counter the communist rebels when they launched a rebellion in the Congo but were crushed by mercenaries led by Mike. Soon after, Tshombe ended up forming a secessionist government. Mad Mike claimed that he and his men had killed between 5,000 and 10,000 people and was later featured in the BBC 24 Hours programme in 1969 (Vice). One might say that Mad

Mike's actions in Congo reflect the ethical dangers of using mercenaries in conflict zones, where a lack of accountability can result in severe human rights abuses. His role as a mercenary shows an early example of how private military actors went from being rogue soldiers into an organised corporation.

At the same time, many nations experienced political and economic breakdowns, leading to widespread instability. For example, countries in Africa, such as Somalia and Sierra Leone, witnessed civil wars, creating areas of instability for PMFs to operate in (Singer 50). Moreover, with the end of the bipolar world some governments that relied on the Soviet Union and the United States for protection found themselves without the resources to sustain their armies or control their territories (Singer 51). According to the British Army officer Tim Spicer, a prominent figure in the private military industry, as reported by Andrew Gilligan in 1998:

The end of the Cold War has allowed conflicts long suppressed or manipulated by the superpowers to reemerge. At the same time, most armies have got smaller and live footage on CNN of United States soldiers being killed in Somalia has had staggering effects on the willingness of governments to commit to foreign conflicts.

Colonel Spicer's observation of the post-1991 era resonates with Singer's security gap idea. However, Spicer mentioned how the news footage of U.S. troops being killed in places like Somalia led to a significant decrease in public and governmental willingness to commit to foreign interventions. This made it easier for PMFs to grow, as these companies are not part of the regular army; they can operate without the same level of political and public oversight.

The collapse of the Soviet Union was characterised by globalization. In brief, globalization is a term used to describe the increasing connectedness and interdependence of world cultures and economies ("Globalization"). Many scholars noted that opening economies and expanding multinational corporations (MNCs) into previously inaccessible international

markets (Singer 49) profoundly affected global security and economic systems. Globalization has helped create wealth and opportunities for some; however, for others, it has widened inequalities. As Singer noted, this imbalance led to a world where “peace in the West, war for the rest,” leaving vulnerable people behind. The scholar argues that globalization caused social problems such as poverty, malnutrition, and marginalization. These issues have mostly fallen unfairly on the youngest portion of the population, in places like Sub-Saharan Africa and parts of South Asia, where poverty rates are high. Those youth are often undereducated and excluded from formal economic systems, they become prime recruits for PMFs. For instance, in countries like Angola and Sierra Leone, PMFs have recruited former child soldiers and unemployed youth to serve in conflict zones, exploiting their desperation and lack of alternatives (Rinaldi and Irrera).

Alongside this, globalization also contributed to the flood of weapons and ex-soldiers into the global market. With the end of the Cold War, the former Communist nations and most Western powers armies reached historic lows. This massive discharge left elite units like the former U.S. Navy SEALs Erik Prince looking for somewhere else to employ their expertise. These ex-soldiers were tempted by flexible contracts and higher pay, One example of this is a memo released at the hearing, which shows that some of the paid Blackwater militia were making as much as \$1,200 per day, exceeding military pay (Erbe). At the same time, the Cold War flooded the globe with tools of large-scale violence. For instance, the new unified Germany auctioned off East Germany’s entire arsenal to private buyers (Singer 54). Keith Krause, a professor at the United Nations, said researchers had concluded that an estimated 550 million small arms are floating around the globe. This made light arms cheap and easily accessible. In Uganda, for example, an assault rifle like the AK-47 costs as little as a chicken (UN).

1.4 Outsourcing War: Lessons from Iraq and the All-Volunteer Force Dilemma

Outsourcing has always been about cost savings. Now, in modern warfare, outsourcing military functions has expanded beyond just logistics and support roles. As Singer notes in an

interview with Vice Media, PMCs have taken on “all the different roles of war,” including consulting, training, back-end logistics, and even tactical battlefield operations. This change signifies a fundamental update in how the U.S. fights its wars. For example, there were more private contractors than U.S. troops during the Iraq War. By 2008, Iraq represented one of the most privatized military operations in American history, with the U.S. Department of Defense employing 155,826 private contractors there compared to 152,275 troops (Dunigan).

Additionally, PMCs follow the same standards for law enforcement and combat as nations. As a result, they follow regulations at the national, regional, and international levels, participate in combat using conventional weapons, and follow an established line of command. However, some PMCs seek to avoid these engagements during the recruitment process since they lack formal hiring checks (Jager and Ortiz 60-61). A notable example comes several years following the beginning of the Iraq War in 2003. Blackwater, under contract with the United States and with the consent of the Iraqi government, had provided armed security personnel to protect U.S. Department of State officials. On 16 September 2007, Blackwater employees caused a big issue in Baghdad. After reportedly coming under attack, they engaged in a gunfight that left 14 civilians dead and thirteen injured. Although Blackwater described their actions as self-defense, the Iraqi government accused the firm of randomly opening fire, labeling the event a "crime" (Singer 253).

The U.S. relationship with Iraq suffered greatly as a result of the incident. It showed how risky it can be to depend on PMCs. After the Iraqi government said they were revoking Blackwater's license, it turned out the company never had a proper one in the first place. This revealed the absence of supervision and control in the private military sphere. In addition, if Blackwater were banned, the U.S. State Department, which mostly depended on the company for diplomatic protection, would have no other option. This dependency forced Secretary of State Condoleezza Rice to intervene and ask the Iraqi Prime Minister to allow Blackwater to remain, undermining broader U.S. efforts to push Iraq toward political reforms (Singer 253).

Years later, in December 2020, President Donald Trump granted pardons to four Blackwater contractors involved in the Nisour Square massacre of 2007. These contractors had been convicted for the deaths of 14 civilians, including two children. The pardons sparked international outrage and reopened debates over the accountability of PMCs (Safi).

The military trend towards outsourcing can be traced back to the establishment of the all-volunteer force (AVF) in 1973. It was announced by the Secretary of Defense Melvin R. Laird (U.S. Department of Defense). An all-volunteer force is a military where individuals choose to serve voluntarily, rather than being required to do so through conscription⁴. While the AVF has been widely regarded as a success by the deputy defense secretary Kathleen H. Hicks, it also introduced new challenges. As the U.S. military continued to operate without the draft, it faced growing issues with manpower shortages and rising costs. According to Ashish Vazirani, Under Secretary of Defense for Personnel and Readiness, in 1995, 40% of young people had a parent who served in the U.S. military. Still, by 2022, this number had dropped to just 12%. This decline likely reduced their interest in joining the military. Maintaining the AVF has also been increasingly expensive. Since the end of the draft, the military has had to offer competitive pay and benefits to attract volunteers. By 2001, military pay has increased by 80%, and the cost of supporting each active-duty service member has nearly reached \$400,000 per year (Punaro and Jones).

As of 2024, only 23% of young Americans meet the physical, mental, and moral standards required to join the U.S. Army. The rest are disqualified due to issues like obesity and drug use. To address this, the U.S. military introduced a “Future Soldier Prep Course” to help underqualified recruits meet military standards, which, in turn, adds to the overall cost of maintaining a capable force (Baldor). These rising costs might have helped make outsourcing to PMCs an attractive alternative, as private contractors can offer a variety of services at a fraction of the cost.

⁴ Conscription, also known as the draft, is a system where the government legally requires able-bodied citizens to serve in the military.

1.5 Research Gap

The increased reliance on private contractors in the post-9/11 period raises multiple questions of effectiveness, transparency, and accountability, highlighting the need for a deeper exploration of whether they helped or hindered the U.S. objectives. Therefore, this study aims to explore the following question:

How did the use of private military contractors in Afghanistan affect U.S. strategic objectives?

To explore the overarching question of how private military contractors influenced U.S. strategic objectives in Afghanistan, this study addresses several sub-questions:

RQ1. Did the use of private military contractors support or undermine the US strategic objectives,

RQ2. How did the issues of transparency and accountability shape the performance and perception of private contractors in the conflict?

This dissertation critically examines the role of private military contractors in Afghanistan, analyzing both their contributions and drawbacks. It focuses on how their involvement influenced the operational effectiveness of U.S. military missions, affected relationships with the Afghan population, and raised questions of transparency, accountability, and financial gain. RQ should be included

In the subsequent chapters, this dissertation will disprove the theory, claimed by advocates for military contracting, that the commercialisation of government services decreases costs and increases quality of these goods and services, thereby benefiting the public purse. Instead, the paper will show that military contracting is at least as expensive, and often more expensive, than if the military were to perform the same services in-house.

1.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter has traced the evolution of private military privatisation, from early contractors support in the Continental Army to the modern use of PMCs in conflict zones, as seen in the Iraq War. The historical analysis shows how military outsourcing evolved over the years as a cost-saving tactic, slowly shifting roles from logistical support to actual combat and strategic operations. While this background establishes a foundation for understanding the privatized military industry, the United States reaction to the terrorist attacks of September 11 marked a key turning point. Although the government's quick response has been well documented, the question of who has profited from this war has received less attention. This chapter concludes by identifying the research gap and outlining the main questions that the dissertation aims to address.

Chapter II: America's Longest War

2.1 Introduction

The U.S. involvement in Afghanistan far predates the 21st century, stretching back decades, often referred to as the longest war in American history. It began with an international coalition led by President George W. Bush in response to the 9/11 attacks. Spanning over two decades, this conflict cost the U.S. roughly \$290 million daily for more than 7,300 days, funding military operations, reconstruction, and private contractors, according to Brown University's Costs of War project. Yet, the human cost was even greater: By 2020, over 100,000 civilians and over 60,000 security forces have been killed (Al Jazeera; UN News). This chapter examines the hidden costs of military privatization in Afghanistan, examining how historical decisions—from the Soviet invasion to post-9/11 policies—intertwined with an increasing reliance on private military contractors (PMCs). It investigates how this outsourcing led to corruption, waste, and unforeseen consequences, raising critical questions about whether the use of PMCs helped or harmed U.S. goals in the region.

2.2 Historical Context

2.2.1 Soviet Invasion, Mujahideen, and the Rise of the Taliban

During the Cold War, both the U.S. and the Soviet Union sought to gain footholds in Afghanistan, first through infrastructure investments and then military intervention by the Soviets in 1979 (Stewart). The argument for the Afghanistan invasion was that the newly formed communist government had invited them. Their shared goal was to transform the country into a socialist state, although they were able to capture the major towns, most Afghans lived in mountains, where people were poor, conservative, and devoted to Islam and different tribal traditions. Therefore, authority for many Afghans came from their tribal leaders. When the new Communist government attempted to impose land reforms and abolish social codes, rural Afghans resisted and formed militias known as the Mujahideen (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica).

Bin Laden joined the Mujahideen after the Soviets began bombing the villages, which led to more Afghans joining as well. He was one of the founders of Maktab al-Khidamat in 1984, which attracted more foreign fighters from various Muslim nations. These militias received funding from other powers such as the U.S (Wright 145). While providing arms to the Mujahideen appeared to be an effective short-term tactic for undermining the Soviet Union at the start, it ultimately proved to have severe long-term consequences, as evidenced by the rise of the Taliban.

In 1989, the Soviets withdrew from Afghanistan. Shortly after, the Mujahideen disbanded into factions, leading Afghanistan into civil war and terrorizing the population. In Kandahar in 1994, a group of local villagers asked for assistance from Mohammed Omar, a former fighter in the Soviet conflict who had since transitioned to a teaching job. He and several other teachers gathered a group of students and forced the Mujahideen out, thereby gaining complete control of Kandahar. This group that brought peace to Kandahar after many bloody years became known as the Taliban, meaning "the Students" in Pashto. As they moved northward, they seized control of the major highways in the country, which helped fund their expansion through taxation and the regulation of growing opium regions. Pakistan feared one of the many militias in Afghanistan would take power and get support from India, so they supplied the Taliban with an abundance of weapons.

In 1996, Bin Laden declared war on the United States, and the Taliban seized control over the country after entering Kabul. They exclusively appointed Pashtuns, who were inexperienced and without any practical knowledge on how to govern (Ellis). The civil war created a power vacuum that allowed the Taliban to emerge as a stabilising force, at least initially, highlighting how political instability and fragile local government may create opportunities for extremist groups.

2.2.2 9/11 and U.S. intervention

Then came the events of September 11, 2001, which shocked the world. Americans woke up to a historic tragedy. Their country was under attack, hit by a series of unexpected events. First, a plane crashed into the World Trade Centre at 8:46 am. In the beginning, people thought it was just a tragic accident, then a second plane hit the other tower at 9:03 am. The attackers set the buildings on fire, trapping people inside and filling New York City with smoke. Within two hours, both towers collapsed, leaving a thick cloud of dust. At 9:37 am, a third plane crashed into the Pentagon, the huge military base near Washington DC. The fourth plane crashed in a field in Pennsylvania at 10:03 am. The passengers on the plane fought back against the attackers. It seems that the attackers planned to crash the plane into the Capitol Building in Washington DC (Bergen and L; figure 2). This made it clear that these were not accidents, but deliberate attacks. In total, almost 3,000 people died in the attacks, most of them in New York. The attacks were carried out by nineteen hijackers, primarily Saudi Arabian citizens like Bin Laden himself, with a few from other Middle Eastern countries. They were affiliated with the terrorist group Al-Qaeda (Jackson, 2024).

Fig. 2. Flight Paths of 9/11 Attacks

Source: Texas Higher Education Coordinating Board

After the plane crash incidents, the United States, with the support of NATO, the Mujahideen, and over 40 countries, invaded Afghanistan under ‘Operation Enduring Freedom’ in 2001 (Hew; Ellis). By deploying large numbers of private military contractors (PMCs) alongside its army, the U.S. effectively normalised their use, giving them a degree of legitimacy within the context of the invasion. While the initial objective was to capture Osama Bin Laden, the mastermind behind the September 11 attacks, the goals of the war quickly evolved. A month after the start of the conflict, the Taliban offered to turn over Bin Laden. However, President Bush rejected this (The Washington Post), indicating that the Bush Administration did not genuinely explore any alternatives to war. Instead, the focus shifted toward destroying and overthrowing the Taliban system in Afghanistan, which had provided a safe haven for the terrorists. The broader goal became creating a new democratic authority in the country (Malkasian 460; Xu 45).

To strengthen public support for the war back home, the U.S. introduced democracy and women's rights as moral matters. This narrative resonated with many Americans, including Laura Bush, First Lady of the US from 2001 to 2009: “The plight of women and children in Afghanistan is a matter of deliberate human cruelty. The fight against terrorism is also a fight for the rights and dignity of women” (Radio Address, 2001). While these ideal objectives were presented as central to the mission, they might also serve another less publicised purpose: preventing the Taliban from returning to power.

2.3 Post-9/11 Military Spending Surge

Journalist Jimmy Burns observed that “it is perhaps an awkward but unsettling truth that the events of September 11, which brought such pain and tragedy to so many people, has given the corporate security world a new lease on life” (qtd. in Singer 232). In the aftermath of the 9/11 terrorist attacks, the global economy struggled with the drop in stock markets, and sectors like aviation and insurance faced reduced consumer confidence (Josephs; Fox). However, PMCs saw their stock prices jump by 50% or more, thanks to the increased spending on security by

businesses, creating a “security tax” on the global economy, as Singer puts it (Singer 232). The corporate security world capitalised on global anxiety, showing how crises can be commercialised and monetised under the cover of protection.

The U.S. government's response to the terrorist attacks, like the “War on Terror,” directly boosted the private security industry. A Defense Department official even joked about it, stating publicly, “The war on terrorism is the full employment act for these guys” (Schrader), suggesting that they might have created a self-sustaining cycle of conflict and profited heavily from it. As it wasn't just corporations that responded with major investments in security—the American government also drastically increased military spending. The Pentagon's budget from 2002 to 2003 grew so much that the increase alone was larger than the entire military budget of any other country, including major powers like China, Russia, the United Kingdom, Germany, and France (Hartung 3).

The Pentagon's spending (including regular spending and special war funds) jumped by over 10% in the first year alone. This was not a one-time boost; the Pentagon's budget kept growing for 10 straight years, something never seen before in U.S. history. By 2010, military spending hit a peak of over \$800 billion, surpassing even the highest spending during the Korean War, Vietnam War, or Cold War era (Reagan buildup). This surge in spending could reflect a shift in U.S. policy: treating global conflicts as permanent investments rather than temporary interventions, likely driven by the ongoing War on Terror.

Fig. 3. The Pentagon Budget from 1948-2020 (in Billions of 2021 USD)

Source: Brown University

This surge in spending, unprecedented in U.S. history, reflects a policy shift toward treating global conflicts as permanent investments. In 2023, the U.S. spent over \$800 billion on its military, dwarfing the combined budgets of the top ten nations (Tian et al. 2). With nearly 800 bases across 70 countries, compared to 30 for Britain, France, and Russia combined (Vine), this global presence comes with financial challenges. Repeated Pentagon audits⁵ show 61% of assets unaccounted for, with the sixth consecutive audit failure in 2024 (Gledhill), creating loopholes that allow PMCs to exploit and profit without accountability. This environment enabled companies like Lockheed Martin and Raytheon to secure billions in contracts (see Table 2), raising questions about the effectiveness and transparency of outsourcing military functions.

⁵ The Pentagon audit is an annual review that checks whether the U.S. Department of Defense (DOD) can properly account for its assets, including military equipment, weapons, and funds.

The rise in funding also changed how military operations were conducted, which resulted in an increasing reliance on private companies to handle tasks previously handled by government personnel. The switch toward outsourcing is evident in defence spending patterns; data shows that contracts currently account for around 54% of the Pentagon's budget authority (DOD). This increase in reliance on private military contractors confirms the growing trend of outsourcing military functions and raises numerous questions about effectiveness, transparency, and accountability.

Notably, according to 19 years worth of data from the top 100 contractors list pulled from “SAM.gov,” we see the same name of PMC appearing repeatedly. While there was once a wide variety of defence contractors, the industry has consolidated over the last two decades, transitioning from 51 to 5 aerospace and defence prime contractors (State of Competition within the Defense Industrial Base DOD 23). This consolidation has led to billions of dollars flowing to a handful of firms. In fact, the 2022 report of the State of Competition within the Defense Industrial Base warns that “DOD is increasingly reliant on a small number of contractors for critical defence capabilities” (DOD 1).

The benefits of the post-9/11 increase in Pentagon spending have been unequally distributed. In recent years, about 30% of all Pentagon contracts have gone to just five major weapons companies: Lockheed Martin, Boeing, General Dynamics, Raytheon, and Northrop Grumman. Together, these “Big Five” companies received over \$286 billion in contracts between 2019 and 2020 (see Table 2). This could suggest that the Pentagon is not just dealing with outsourcing, but with a growing monopoly inside its own defence operations.

Table 2. Pentagon Prime Contracts Issued to the Top Five Weapons Contractors

From FY 2019 to 2020 (in \$Billions)

	FY 2019 Awards (\$ Billions)	FY 2020 Awards (\$Billions)
Lockheed Martin	47.1	75.2
Raytheon	26.3	27.8
General Dynamics	16.5	21.8
Boeing	15.6	21.7
Northrop Grumman	14.2	20.3

Source: Hartung, Profits of War, based on Federal Procurement Data System, p. 5.

2.4 Who Profits from the War Economy?

Today the Department of Defense (DOD) spending on military contracts is more than 2.5 times what it was in 2001. Major U.S. based weapons makers have benefitted financially the most from the post-9/11 military spending surge, as seen in Table 2. However, weapons contractors were not the only ones who benefitted. Companies that have taken advantage of the buildup of the last 20 years range from logistics and reconstruction companies like Kellogg, Brown and Root (KBR) and Bechtel, to weapons manufacturers like Raytheon and Lockheed Martin, to armed private security contractors like Blackwater and Dyncorp. About half of the Pentagon budget—\$370 billion in 2019, went to military contractors for both continuing peacetime operations and war-related projects, as Heidi Peltier pointed out in her study of the "camo economy" (Peltier 4). According to the Congressional Research Service, that number grew to \$420 billion in 2020, meaning more than half of the total Pentagon budget now goes to private

companies instead of the national armed forces. This trend might suggest how the PMC’s support is no longer just an option — it has become a core part of how the U.S. fights its wars and maintains global security.

The first way contractors have profited from the post-9/11 wars is through logistics and reconstruction work in the war zones. The chaos of war, the lack of adequate government oversight, and the sheer volume of funds poured into the reconstruction effort in a short time frame all contributed to an environment that enabled massive waste, fraud and abuse in the reconstruction efforts in Iraq and Afghanistan.

Fig. 4. US foreign aid by category, adjusted for inflation, 1946–2022 (in Billions USD)

Source: US Agency for International Development

Its invasion of Afghanistan in October 2001 showed how much the U.S. depends on private companies to assist its military. Following it, foreign aid began to increase, as Figure 4 shows. Despite the U.S. military withdrawal and recent reductions in aid, Afghanistan has received a significant amount of U.S. foreign aid since then and continues to rank in the top 5 nations, along with Israel and Ukraine, that get the most help in the form of economic and

military support (US Agency for International Development). But the U.S. faced a paradox: while pouring billions into rebuilding Afghanistan, it was at the same time waging a war on it. The American military was hunting down Taliban and al-Qaeda members and funding Mujahideen leaders in exchange for their help, but it backfired as these drone strikes killed innocent civilians. The Mujahideen began terrorising people, gradually becoming warlords (Stewart). These contradictions might have exposed deeper flaws in U.S. policy: prioritising short-term military goals over sustainable reconstruction. Moreover, the billions spent on "rebuilding" were often wasted through corruption, mismanagement, and obvious fraud.

This waste was no accident. Companies (like the ones shown in table 2) profit from war in at least three ways: logistics and reconstruction, providing weapons, and contracting for private security. As revealed in the American political scientist William D. Hartung's 2021 paper on war profiteering, contractors were able to overcharge or commit fraud, thanks to the wartime chaos, where speed of delivery outweighed oversight. The first way contractors have profited from the post-9/11 wars is through logistics and reconstruction work in the war zones.

The U.S. spent \$7 billion on anti-drug efforts in Afghanistan, which eventually failed to stop the production of drugs and even weakened other strategic objectives. In 2001, Afghanistan officially became a narco-state due to the unprecedented growth of its poppy industry (Felbab-Brown 189). Poppy flowers provide opium for the development of a class of analgesics and antalgics called Opiates, which are used to relieve pain, they can be addictive. Because the early attempts to eliminate this business were ineffective and counterproductive. They fueled anger among people and sparked violent protests, and most importantly, they forced poor farmers into joining the Taliban, who provided both protection and financial rewards in exchange for loyalty.

Perhaps one of the most well-known reconstruction projects in Afghanistan is what ended up being the "World's Most Expensive Gas Station.". In an effort to promote alternative energy, the US Department of Defense spent nearly \$43 million to construct a compressed natural gas

(CNG) filling station as an alternative fuel source in northern Afghanistan while being unable to provide an explanation for its absurd cost. “The Pentagon charged the American taxpayers \$43m for what is likely to be the world’s most expensive gas station,” said John Sopko, head of the SIGAR⁶ (The Guardian). Hartungs notes that a similar compressed natural gas filling station in neighboring Pakistan costs no more than \$500,000 to construct (Hartungs 10). That would make the petrol station in Afghanistan 140 times more expensive, suggesting a lack of oversight that allowed contractors to inflate costs.

A 2021 report from SIGAR found that no feasibility study was conducted prior to construction, and Afghanistan lacked the infrastructure (e.g., pipelines and vehicles) to support CNG use. A small Central Asian engineering firm received the contract without any competitive bidding, raising suspicions of profiteering or bias. By 2021, the station was abandoned, with no evidence of any local or economic benefits. The station was completed in 2014 but was never used operationally (SIGAR, "DOD Task Force" 12-18). This case might expose a critical flaw in post-war planning: contractors often profit more from inflated costs than from delivering functional projects, which points in the direction that financial gain for the contractor is more important than mission success.

Another example, touching on the logistics side, shows a similarly bizarre waste of money. In October 2010, the U.S. government allocated \$3 million for eight inflatable boats intended to assist the Afghan National Police in safeguarding rural Afghan waterways and combating smuggling on the Amu Darya river, which forms the border between Afghanistan and Uzbekistan. Less than nine months later, these boats were considered unnecessary and never deployed. They were kept unused in a Navy warehouse in Yorktown, Virginia (Keneally). Each of the eight boats costs approximately \$375,000; similar boats in the U.S. are typically sold for \$50,000 (Sieff and Davenport).

⁶ SIGAR was created by Congress to provide independent and objective oversight of Afghanistan reconstruction projects and activities.

What raises suspicion even higher, according to the CIA website, Afghanistan is not only landlocked⁷ but primarily consists of mountains, lacking any water within its borders. The unnamed U.S. based supplier who won the \$375,000 boats' contract had inflated the cost by 650% ("Afghanistan - The World Factbook"). With no evidence that the Afghan National Police ever requested or were capable of operating and maintaining the boats, it's likely they were never used at all. Their eventual abandonment in a Navy warehouse suggests that poor planning and possibly exaggerated expenses for profit played a major role in this wasteful spending decision.

The second source of income for contractors during the war was through private security services—protecting critical U.S. facilities, personnel, and infrastructure, especially in large-scale reconstruction programs, where firms were hired not just for protection but also for luxury. Between 2009 and 2012, the Pentagon sent American business experts to Afghanistan to help jump-start the country's economy after the war. During that time, the U.S. Task Force for Business and Stability Operations (TFBSO⁸) spent more than \$800 million until the Pentagon shut it down in March 2015.

The goal behind the TFBSO was possibly a valid approach—connecting American and Afghan business interests to help develop Afghanistan's economic sector. Everyone would make money, and Afghanistan would receive much-needed infrastructure and jobs. "We do capitalism. We're about helping companies make money," former TFBSO director Paul A. Brinkley told *The Washington Post* back in 2011 (Chandrasekaran). However, similar to the previous American reconstruction efforts in Afghanistan, TFBSO ended up being destroyed by a mix of corruption, ignorance, and poor decision-making. Instead of using nearby military bases for housing, TFBSO leadership rented luxury villas and spent nearly \$150 million creating high-end living spaces for a small number of U.S. advisors—estimated to be between five and ten staff. These villas came

⁷ A country is considered "landlocked" when it is entirely surrounded by land and has no direct access to the sea or ocean.

⁸ The Task Force for Business and Stability Operations (TFBSO) was a U.S. program created to boost economic growth in conflict zones. In Afghanistan, it aimed to support businesses and create jobs but was often criticized for wasting money and failing to deliver results.

with private chefs, full-time bodyguards, and round-the-clock support, even though cheaper and safer government facilities were available. Between 2010 and 2014, TFBSO also paid over \$57 million to Triple Canopy, a private security firm, for armed protection. Triple Canopy, owned by the company Academi (previously known as Blackwater), was one of several firms that profited heavily from this arrangement (SIGAR 3, 11-15). While the goal was to bring prosperity to Afghanistan, much of the spending ended up serving the comfort and protection of a few U.S. advisors—doing little to support actual economic development on the ground.

The third major source of profit for contractors was in supplying weapons, ammunition, and military equipment. The post-9/11 surge in defense spending wasn't just about services and security; it also meant billions in contracts for tanks, aircraft, armored vehicles, and combat gear. But even more money flowed into smaller, less visible items—guns, bullets, and related equipment—that were often bought in bulk with little transparency. According to a 2016 analysis by Action on Armed Violence, a UK-based NGO, the Pentagon allocated contracts for more than \$40 billion worth of guns and ammunition between September 2001 and 2015. This included 1.45 million firearms, as part of \$2.16 billion worth of small arms contracts designated for Afghanistan. Billions more were spent equipping U.S. troops deployed to the war zone, but the full amount remains unknown. Neither the Pentagon, Congress, nor independent analysts have been able to account for the total spending in this category. One might say that the scale of U.S. military spending in Afghanistan, combined with the inability to fully account for it, raises serious concerns about transparency and oversight in defense contracting.

2.5 Chapter Summary

The U.S. intervention in Afghanistan exposed a mind boggling contradiction: while the U.S. was spending billions to rebuild the country, it was at the same time waging a war on it. The private military industry profited heavily from the self-sustaining cycle of conflict it created. The three major sources of profit—logistics and reconstruction, private security, and weapons

supply—help explain how the post-9/11 wars became deeply commercialized. In each of the above cases, the conditions of war allowed contractors to operate with limited oversight, inflate costs, and suffer minimal consequences. Patterns of companies profiting from unnecessary gear, services with exaggerated importance, or overpriced supplies were common. Contractors often pushed unnecessary equipment and services, exploiting the Department of Defense’s wartime budget flexibility to maximize profit. These are just a few examples of the waste and fraud during the U.S.’s longest war. The full extent of mismanaged American taxpayer dollars is likely many times greater, hidden under thousands of poorly tracked transactions.

Chapter III: Profits Over Purpose

3.1 Introduction

The Taliban's immediate takeover of Afghanistan upon the U.S.'s departure is often viewed as proof that the Afghanistan War was a failure. On the contrary, from the perspective of some of the most powerful people in the U.S., it may have been an extraordinary success. Notably, the boards of directors of all five major defense contractors include retired top-level military officers. Since U.S. military actions in Afghanistan were approved in September 2001, the stocks of the top five defense companies has increased by around 900%. This chapter explores the financial and political factors that enabled a select group of individuals and corporations to profit immensely from the conflict, often at the expense of the U.S. mission. In this chapter, I shall first present the benefits that come with PMCs before moving on to discuss their drawbacks. Through detailed case studies of both Afghan and American individuals and companies, the last chapter attempts to highlight how the privatization of military functions in Afghanistan created a war economy that prioritized profit over purpose.

3.2 Assessing the Strategic Contributions of Private Military Contractors in Afghanistan

3.2.1 Positive Outcomes of PMC Engagement

While military privatization is often criticized for fueling corruption and waste, as we saw in chapter II, it is also important to examine the arguments made by the advocates of using contractors in Afghanistan. First, private military contractors were seen by many as flexible tools for sustaining a long-term war effort without the political risks of large-scale troop deployment. Practically speaking, contractors helped reduce the workload on U.S. military personnel and took on risks that would otherwise have fallen on uniformed service members. The second perceived advantage was the argument that using contractors could be cheaper than deploying government employees. Unlike military personnel, contractors could be hired temporarily and dismissed when their services were no longer needed (Hammes 2). This is further supported by the growing reliance on advanced weapons systems technology by the U.S. Army, particularly when the task is

so complex that it is not economically beneficial for the military to maintain, troubleshoot, and keep up with the rapid technological change (Saballa).

Continuity was also a major advantage of contractors, although the U.S. military has a policy that ensures the vast majority of personnel rotate every 6 to 12 months, contractors are often willing to stay for much longer (Johnson). Companies may offer bonuses to employees who remain, which sometimes could result in a deeper understanding of the situation. However, the main argument made in support of PMCs was their ability to reduce the visible human cost of war. A 2010 report showed that contractor deaths in Afghanistan had begun to exceed those of U.S. military personnel. These casualties were not included in official Pentagon figures and were instead reported through the U.S. Department of Labor, which made them largely invisible in the public discourse. As a result, there was no national outcry when contractors were injured or killed. This invisibility helped policymakers avoid the kind of public backlash that rising military deaths might have triggered (Hammes 3). In other words, PMCs allowed the war effort to continue with fewer political consequences.

Lastly, it is crucial to acknowledge that some contractors were not just motivated by profit, but were veterans returning to serve in different roles. For example, Erik Prince, the founder of Blackwater, whom I mentioned in chapter 1, is a former Navy SEAL. In an interview with VICE Media, he shared that he founded Blackwater to maintain a connection with his SEAL team, stating: "We did exactly the job the U.S. government hired us to do and did it well, more than 100,000 missions on the security side," underscoring that their commitment matched that of active-duty service members. Similarly, former U.S. soldier Phillip Mills, also featured in the same VICE documentary, attributed his decision to leave the army to insufficient compensation for his contributions. As he put it: "Certainly in my era, anybody who is any good in the army isn't in the army anymore." His comment highlights how, for many skilled soldiers, the private security sector has become a more attractive and rewarding path.

3.2.2 Negative Outcomes of PMC Engagement

Despite the perceived benefits, PMCs also created serious problems—ranging from poor oversight to corruption—that harmed the core mission objectives they were meant to support. When deployed in conflict zones like Afghanistan, especially in the context of counterterrorism—in this case, the Taliban—contractors introduced a number of problems at both tactical and strategic levels.

One of the main concerns is that the government does not control the quality or training of the personnel that private contractors hire. A clear example is Aegis Defence Services, a London-based firm awarded a \$497 million contract by the U.S. Department of State in 2011 to manage security operations at the U.S. Embassy in Kabul (Ross). According to *The Guardian*, in 2011 Aegis expanded its recruitment to include personnel from African countries because they were cheaper than European contractors. A former senior director at a British firm alleged that Aegis had employed former child soldiers from Sierra Leone, paying them just \$16 per day to guard U.S. government sites in Afghanistan. James Ellery, who was a director of Aegis Defence Services between 2005 and 2015, explained the company’s cost-driven logic. In his own words:

You probably would have a better force if you recruited entirely from the Midlands of England, But it can’t be afforded. So you go from the Midlands of England to Nepalese etc etc, Asians, and then at some point you say I’m afraid all we can afford now is Africans. (qtd. in Ross)

This quote, though said in a pragmatic manner, exposes the dehumanizing economics of private security; the phrase “all we can afford now is Africans” is especially shocking, it reveals how military labor in wartime was turned into a commodity, ranked not by experience but by affordability. Under these racial and regional biases, guarding a U.S. embassy in Afghanistan became less about protection and more about price.

3.3 9/11 Afghan Millionaires

While foreign contractors like Aegis exploited vulnerable labor markets, the U.S. counterinsurgency strategy also created opportunities for local profiteering through the 2008 ‘Afghan First’ policy, which aimed to boost the Afghan economy by awarding contracts to Afghan nationals as a way to win hearts and minds (NATO). In practice, this often created a class of ‘9/11 millionaires’ who grew wealthy thanks to their close ties with the U.S. military, sometimes at the expense of the mission objectives (Safi). Fahim Hashimy, a former English teacher in Kabul, demonstrates this trend. In 2001, he was hired as an interpreter by U.S. and British forces when they arrived in Afghanistan. He later started a small company supplying military bases with goods and fuel. By 2021, the Hashimy Group had grown into a large company with a TV station, manufacturing facilities, real estate investments, trucking, and a small airline startup, all based in Afghanistan (Wilkie). While Hashimy’s success met economic goals, most contracts went to his company due to the trust and loyalty he built as an interpreter, potentially fueling hatred and undermining the ‘Afghan First’ policy objectives.

Fig. 5. US troop levels in Afghanistan 2001-2017

Source: Vox

Hashimy’s story, however, seems transparent compared to Hikmatullah Shadman, whose actions show a darker side of these contracts. Like Hashimy, Shadman was one of the first Afghan interpreters hired by American troops at the start of the war, after five years of interpreting for soldiers in and around Kandahar. After renting a truck, Shadman started delivering fuel and goods to the American base; he quickly built a network of reliable truckers and subcontractors. As troop levels increased between 2007 and 2012 (see figure 5), so did Shadman’s revenue. In 2009 alone, his company billed the Department of Defense for \$45 million. According to bank records, Shadman's trucking company earned \$167 million from U.S. contracts by 2012. However, Shadman’s success came with serious problems. In 2012, the U.S. Department of Justice accused him of fraud. He allegedly paid kickbacks to American soldiers and Afghan officials to win contracts, inflated his costs, and billed the U.S. government for work never done. Worse yet, investigators tied some of his financial deals to a known Taliban “money man” (Wilkie),

suggesting his actions may have helped the enemy. These issues hindered rebuilding efforts, as money meant for Afghanistan's growth was wasted, showing how the policy failed.

Hashimy's story can be viewed as a rare example of a local Afghan benefiting from the war in a positive way—especially after decades of conflict that have destroyed their country—but it also raises questions about fairness and favouritism. Nevertheless, compared to others, his case stands out as one of the few where something good came out of a bad situation. Shadman's story, by contrast, shows the opposite. It demonstrates how easy it was to get rich through the flawed system created by the US. His rise was not built on creating value or rebuilding his country, but rather on bribery, inflated contracts, and, in the worst cases, deals that may have helped the very enemy the U.S. was fighting.

3.4 9/11 American Billionaires

This problem was not exclusive to Afghans. Americans and foreign contractors with huge contracts did the exact same—sometimes even more—taking advantage of the wartime budget. One of the top suppliers of fresh food to U.S. forces was Netherlands based Supreme Group BV, founded by American Alfred Orenstein. In 2005, Supreme Foodservice signed a deal with the Defense Supply Center of Philadelphia to provide food and water to U.S. forces in Afghanistan. This contract grew the company's revenue by 50 times, reaching \$5.5 billion over six years, and made Orenstein's son, Stephen, a billionaire by 2013, according to Bloomberg (De Jong).

However, behind Supreme's success were questionable activities. In 2009, the company hired the outgoing director of the Defense Logistics Agency, which previously awarded its contracts, to run its U.S. office. A year later, Supreme got a multibillion-dollar contract extension without any bidding, raising questions about fairness (Hartung 11). Between 2005 and 2009, Supreme used a fake United Arab Emirates subcontractor, Jamal Ahli Foods Co., to raise the prices for fresh fruits, vegetables, and bottled water, overcharging the U.S. government by \$48 million. Supreme pleaded guilty to these fraud charges and paid \$389 million in fines, one of the

largest penalties for a defense contractor in 2014 (U.S. Department of Justice; "Defense Contractor Fined"). These actions wasted money meant for the war effort, hurting U.S. goals in Afghanistan and showing how contractors cared more about profits than the mission.

Supreme wasn't alone in profiting from the war. The aforementioned Erik Prince company, Blackwater, also grew rich thanks to the U.S. contracts. Started in 1997 as a small company providing shooting ranges and training facilities in rural North Carolina for the military and police, Blackwater got its first government contract in 2000 for \$204,000 to help train the navy against terrorist attacks (Risen). Prince described his mission for Blackwater as, "We are trying to do for the national security apparatus what FedEx did for the Postal Service," potentially meaning privatizing parts or the entire war. In 2007, several employees of the company had killed 14 civilians in Baghdad's Nisour Square, a massacre we covered in chapter 1. Shortly after the shooting, Blackwater was rebranded several times, first as XE Services and then as Academi, and later merged with another private contractor, Triple Canopy, to become Constellis. That same year, the U.S. government had given Blackwater over one billion dollars in contracts (Hearing on Blackwater USA; Risen). As a result, Mr. Prince's company went from a small contract of \$200,000 to train troops domestically to sending troops abroad to participate in war zones like Afghanistan, all within a few years and earning a billion dollars in the process.

3.5 A Case Study of Two Young Americans known as 'War Dogs'

While figures like Erik Prince and companies like Supreme Group made billions during the War on Terror—often escaping accountability despite major scandals—others, with far less power and protection, did not get the same treatment. The case of Efraim Diveroli and David Packouz, two young Americans who landed one of the biggest arms contracts of the Afghanistan war, exposes the unequal consequences of corruption in the privatized war economy. Their story, which lacks the political connections or legacy of major defense giants (Vice), helps reveal how justice in this system isn't about what you did but more about who you are.

In the beginning, working from Miami Beach under the name of his father's company, AEY⁹, Diveroli specialized in bidding through online platforms like FedBizOpps on smaller contracts for items like helmets and ammunition for U.S. Special Forces. His early contracts were relatively small, but they gave AEY a track record that the Pentagon requires for companies that want to bid on large defense contracts (Western). His business plan was simple but highly influential. Most companies grow by attracting more customers. Diveroli realized he could succeed by selling to one big customer: the U.S. military. In the USA, no government agency buys and sells more than the Defense Department; everything from fighter jets to paper clips and loaders. By law, every Pentagon purchase order is required to be open to public bidding, and under the Bush administration, small businesses like AEY were guaranteed a share of the arms deals. Diveroli didn't have to make any of the products to bid on the contracts. He could broker the deals and find the cheapest prices and underbid the competition (Lawson). All he had to do was win even a tiny fraction of the billions the Pentagon spends on arms every year, and he would have become a millionaire.

In May 2007, they won a large contract to supply 100 million rounds of AK-47 ammunition to the Afghan National Army. Valued at \$298 million, this deal aimed to strengthen the Afghan National Army against the Taliban. Progress in the war had stalled. After six years of fighting, the Taliban were on the rise, Al Qaeda remained a threat, and NATO casualties were rapidly increasing. For the Bush administration, the ammunition was part of the final attempt to turn the war around before next year's U.S. presidential election (Chivers). According to Packouz and Diveroli, the shipment was part of a major arms deal that promised to make them super rich. However, they weren't used to the pressures of being international arms dealers.

Only months earlier, then 23 years old Packouz had been making his living as a massage therapist; his studies at the Educating Hands School of Massage had not included classes in military contracting or geopolitics. However, he couldn't resist the temptation when Diveroli, his

⁹ AEY refers to AEY Inc., the name of the private defense contractor. It is not an acronym.

19 year old high school dropout friend offered him the opportunity to join his expanding arms business. The two friends began their work equipped with nothing more than an internet connection, a few cellphones, and a steady supply of cannabis. (Lawson). They accomplished the ammo contract—100 million rounds of AK-47 ammunition—by obtaining rockets, ammunition, and other supplies that originated from Communist China (which was expressly forbidden) and repackaging it to hide its origin, making it seem like the supplies came from Eastern Europe (Truffaut-Wong and Igoe; Western).

Unlike Blackwater or Supreme Group, AEY didn't have connections in Washington or decades of defense experience. Erik Prince walked free after a massacre in Nisour Square, Supreme Group paid nearly \$400 million in fines for fraud but saw no prison time, Diveroli and Packouz on the other hand were punished quickly and publicly. Both were convicted. Diveroli served federal prison time, while Packouz cooperated and received house arrest (Lawson). Their story exposes a deeper truth: in the world of military privatization, who faces consequences isn't always about the scale of the crime; it's more about the status of the offender. AEY's collapse wasn't just about illegal ammo; it was a lesson in how the business of war tends to overlook certain offenses when committed by entities it deems too important to penalize, while not affording minor players the same grace.

3.6 The Conflicts of Interest inside Congress

While private actors such as Erik Prince, Supreme Foodservice, and the "War Dogs" duo capitalized on the Afghanistan war for personal profit, a quieter yet equally concerning trend saw rise within the U.S. Congress. Several lawmakers, entrusted with approving military budgets and operations, held substantial investments in defense stocks—raising serious ethical questions about conflicts of interest.

Kevin Hern, a member of Congress, holds the largest amount invested in defense stocks. As of 2020, Hern's portfolio was valued at over a million dollars, with more than 80% of that

invested in Honeywell¹⁰ alone, a major aerospace and defense contractor (Moore). Honeywell's stock performance has been strong, particularly since 2009, when Obama deployed a large number of troops to Afghanistan (see Figure 5). As a member of Congress who votes on military engagements and defense budgets, Hern's financial interests are directly affected by these decisions. Furthermore, as chair of the committee's Budget and Spending Task Force, he has a significant influence over war-related actions ("Hern Elected Chairman"). This overlap raises concerns about a potential conflict of interest, where Hern may personally benefit from increased military spending.

Senator Gary Peters, serves on the Armed Services Committee, which authorizes the Pentagon's budget. His 2021 financial disclosures reveal investments in Raytheon Technologies, a major defense contractor known for wartime technologies like missiles and radar systems ("Raytheon: RTX's Raytheon Completes"; "RTX's Raytheon Delivers"). In July 2022, Peters' committee voted to increase defense spending by \$24 billion, far exceeding even President Biden's proposed budget (Ritacco and Mackey). This decision directly benefits companies like Raytheon, in which Peters is a shareholder.

Representative Diana Harshbarger, serves on the House Committee on Homeland Security, with a focus on cybersecurity and infrastructure protection. According to her financial reports, she has assets in six defense firms, with a significant portion in L3Harris Technologies, an IT contractor specializing in defense communications and cybersecurity (Moore). Given her committee role, Harshbarger helps shape policies and funding that impact the cybersecurity sector, directly affecting companies like L3Harris.

The investments of Hern, Peters, and Harshbarger are not isolated cases; they point to a trend of congressmen and women profiteering by investing in defense firms. According to the Sludge analysis, at least 47 members of Congress and their spouses held more than \$6 million in

¹⁰ A multinational American business corporation. It primarily operates in four areas of business: aerospace, building automation, industrial automation, and energy and sustainability solutions.

defense stocks as of August 2021. However, these examples represent only the tip of the iceberg. There are so many more people who abused the system, whom we will never know about, because they never got caught.

3.7 The Pentagon's Revolving Door

While Congress members like Hern, Peters, and Harshbarger profited from defense stocks, a far more systemic corruption festered within the Pentagon itself. As journalist Johnny Harris reveals in his investigation “The Pentagon's Revolving Door,” officials routinely cycle between government roles and lucrative jobs at the same contractors they once regulated.

During the Afghanistan War, the U.S. military became highly dependent on a small group of suppliers for thousands of specialized aircraft spare parts. One example is TransDigm, a company notorious for its practice of acquiring companies that are the sole source of specific parts, then drastically raising the prices. With no considerable competition, TransDigm took advantage of its superior position. According to a 2019 SIGAR report, one of TransDigm's price increases reached 3,800%, and the company refused to provide any justification for the unit price increase on a part needed to support U.S. operations in Afghanistan. Since there was no competition, the Pentagon couldn't compare prices to determine what was fair and reasonable. As a result, it had to award the contract at whatever price TransDigm demanded, just to meet mission requirements and avoid risking weapon systems sitting idle due to a lack of spare parts (Smithberger). This case may confirm the monopoly concerns mentioned earlier.

One might wonder what happens once these companies secure massive profits from Pentagon contracts? A large portion goes toward generous executive compensation, but much of it is also funneled into lobbying efforts aimed at influencing government policy and spending. In the first half of 2023 alone, defense contractors spent nearly \$70 million lobbying the federal government. A significant portion of this lobbying focused on the 2024 National Defense Authorization Act, the annual bill that funds the Pentagon and military operations (Schumer).

Lobbying disclosures show that these efforts were strategically directed at both major political parties—nearly evenly split between Republicans and Democrats.

In terms of overall lobbying expenditures, Lockheed Martin remains at the top of the list. This level of spending raises concerns not only about influence over military budgets, but also about the deep ties between defense contractors and decision-makers inside the U.S. government. An issue often described as the “revolving door,” where former government officials move into private military industry roles and vice versa (SAM.gov)

The revolving door is a metaphorical door between the Pentagon and defense corporations. This allows the movement of retired top military leaders from the Pentagon and the military services into high-paying positions within defense companies and, sometimes, back again into government roles (Lipton). Although the revolving door is metaphorical, it’s also arguably physical. The Pentagon and the headquarters of the Big Five defense contractors are separated only by a highway. In fact, many of these firms are located in an area literally called Pentagon City (see figure 6).

One of the most well-known examples is Jim Mattis. After decades of military service, he retired as a general and joined the board of General Dynamics—a major defense contractor mentioned earlier in Chapter 2. He then returned to government as Secretary of Defense under Trump's first presidency before eventually going back through the “door” to rejoin the board of General Dynamics (Feldscher). He Possibly aimed at bringing with him insider knowledge, government contracts, and influence. This practice is far from rare. A 2023 analysis done by Senator Elizabeth Warren found that top defense companies hired 672 employees directly out of the Pentagon to work as lobbyists, board members, and executives.

Fig. 6. Pentagon and defense contractors headquarters location on the map

Source: Johnny Harris

Finally, defense contractors strategically allocate their operations all across the U.S. map (see figure 7), covering dozens of states and political districts. Setting up an operation creates jobs, which makes them politically popular and well liked by the people. As a result, lawmakers have a strong incentive to support continued military spending, especially when the contracts benefit their own districts. Supporting the defense industry becomes a way to support their voters—and improve their chances of re-election. It is a remarkably strategic move—an example of political engineering at work.

One might see it clearly with lawmakers like Senator Roger Wicker from Mississippi. Wicker serves on the U.S. Senate Committee on Armed Services, which plays a huge role in allocating taxpayer money to the Pentagon, which in turn goes to the contractors. Wicker is

known for strongly supporting increased military spending. In 2024, he wrote an op-ed¹¹ in The New York Times calling for more funding for fighter jets and shipbuilding. "We struggle to build and maintain ships, our fighter jet fleet is dangerously small, and our military infrastructure is outdated" (Wicker).

However, when we look at Wicker's home state, the picture becomes even clearer. The largest employer in Mississippi is a naval shipyard run by a defense contractor called Huntington Ingalls. That means jobs, economic growth, and political support for Wicker. The more contracts that come in, the more favorable people's perception of him becomes in his home state—and the more likely he is to get re-elected. Meanwhile, the U.S. already has the largest aircraft fleet in the world, with over 13,000 aircraft. The second-largest, Russia's, has fewer than 4,000 (FlightGlobal). Yet lawmakers like Wicker continue pushing for more spending, not always based on actual military need, but often because of the economic and political benefits back home.

Defense contractors also understand that Senator Wicker plays a key role in protecting their financial interests, so they contribute large sums to support his political campaigns. These contributions help ensure his re-election, allowing the cycle to continue (OpenSecrets). One might comment that this mutually beneficial relationship between a powerful lawmaker and for-profit defense firms helps explain why the U.S. continues to spend heavily on weapons and programs that may not reflect actual defense needs. Despite the disconnect between the United States' defense spending and its objective necessity, these lawmakers have strong personal and political reasons to consistently advocate for increased military spending, because of the economic and political incentives created by defense contractors.

¹¹ Op-ed (short for "opposite the editorial page") is a type of article in a newspaper where someone expresses their personal opinion on a topic. It is usually written by a guest writer, not the newspaper's editors.

Fig. 7. Top Defense Contractors Facilities Location on The Map

Source: Christian “Mapping the Business of War”

3.8 Chapter Summary

The last chapter attempts to discuss the key findings of the study, which reveal that defense contractors generated enormous financial gains. It examines both Afghan and American individuals and companies, such as Hikmatullah Shadman, Jim Mattis, and Blackwater, exposing their financial gain in the realm of widespread corruption. Moreover, it shows the extreme profitability of military contractors—both those providing services in wartime as well as those producing goods and services in the U.S.— negatively impacts the U.S. labor market by making it more difficult for other firms, or for the military itself, to compete. This is only the tip of the mountain of people who got rich off of Afghanistan. There are so many more people who abused the system, whom we will never know about, because they were never caught.

General Conclusion

This thesis's chapters together reveal that PMCs were first introduced to solve the manpower shortages and increased personnel costs; however, they ultimately failed to address these issues and ended up raising the costs significantly. The first chapter traced the long historical evolution of outsourcing, which was first introduced as a logistics cost-saver, then gradually expanded into combat and critical roles, fundamentally transforming the nature of war. The remaining chapters documented the on-the-ground consequences in Afghanistan. Billions of reconstruction dollars were wasted through corruption, mismanagement, and obvious fraud, as contractors exploited the wartime climate to inflate costs. A clear example was the \$7 billion U.S. anti-narcotics campaigns funded with military dollars, which ultimately fueled poppy production and drove farmers into the arms of the Taliban. Even after the international withdrawal from Afghanistan in August 2021, the PMCs expanded their client list to include U.N. aid agencies and other humanitarian organizations. To facilitate the delivery of essential aid to Afghans facing a severe humanitarian crisis, these organizations needed security to ensure the safety and freedom of movement of their people. As a result, the U.N. has delivered over \$2.9 billion in cash to Afghanistan. While the intention was to provide humanitarian aid, the U.N. says it's unavoidable that some money makes its way to Afghanistan's central bank (@AFGCentralbank), which is managed by a terrorist group who is on an active U.S. sanctions list. That bank then holds an "auction" where groups bid to take those dollars and convert them to the local currency. Every week, the winner of that auction is someone associated with the Haqqani Network, a terror group with ties to Al-Qaeda (Burchett). raising concerns about indirect support to the extremist group.

Although this case study focused on U.S. operations, the findings have global significance. PMCs are now a permanent feature of international security operations. One market research firm estimated that the global PMCs sold \$223 billion worth of services in 2020, a number set to double by 2030. Major powers beyond the United States utilize them; Russia's Wagner Group—despite its officially private status—fights alongside regular troops (Nanda).

Simultaneously, China is increasingly developing its own private military and security companies, deploying them both domestically and internationally to safeguard its expanding interests (Stein). These trends may suggest that the outsourcing of military force is not an isolated American experiment but a global transformation of warfare itself.

To counter these distortions, the thesis argues for a range of policy reforms. First, recognizing that private contractors are here to stay in modern warfare, policymakers must hold the industry to strict standards: transparency and accountability. Every dollar in a PMC contract (including subcontracting) should be traceable by independent auditors and investigative bodies, with real penalties for waste and fraud, regardless of the contractor's size or political connections. Second, legal frameworks must be updated to prevent conflicts of interest within the revolving door between government and industry. Third, making war cheaper and more efficient, in the short term, creates an incentive to wage more of it. Ultimately, the profits of war depend on reducing the reasons for resorting to war in the first place. While private contractors may continue to fill necessary roles in conflict zones, the rules under which they operate must be clearly defined. Only then can states ensure that the business of war does not override the purpose of peace.

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